

Revised checklist of Histeridae (Coleoptera) in the collection of the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia

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Abstract. The present work is devoted to the treatment of the histerid beetles (Histeridae) preserved in the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia. The collection comprises 59 species belonging to 26 genera. The studied material is collected from Bulgaria, Greece, Turkey, Slovakia and Macedonia. New for the Bulgarian fauna are 5 species and 2 genera. Another 10 species are confirmed for the fauna of the country. New distributional data are provided for 32 species.

Key words: Coleoptera, Histeridae, Faunistics, Collection, Europe

Introduction

The insect collections of the National Museum of Natural History, Sofia (NMNHS) (which are the largest on the Balkans) are still not entirely studied. It is especially true for the representatives of the family Histeridae, which are the subjects of this study. Part of the histerid material has already been identified and published by IOAKIMOV (1904), MARKOVICH (1904, 1909), NEDELKOV (1909a, b), ANGELOV (1988), and GUÉORGUIEV (1990). Nevertheless, there are also a lot of unpublished materials kept in the museum.

Nikolai Karnoschitzky has collected the main part of the material (more than 450 specimens), mainly from the Bulgarian Black Sea Coast, and Boryana Zaharieva, chiefly from north-western Bulgaria, the Rhodopes and the region of Bourgas. A few specimens from the first collection were published (KARNOSCHITZKY, 1949, 1959). Except for a few specimens cited by GUÉORGUIEV (1990), the major part of the material of Zacharieva remains untreated. In fact, most of the museum collection of Histeridae is unpublished, as almost half of it has remained unidentified, too.

Material and methods

This study is based on all the available material of Histeridae from the collections of the NMNHS. In total, 1266 specimens were examined and identified. In the groups the information

is ordered according to geographical regions. In the cases when there are more finds from a single locality the repetitions are omitted, using “/” for separation. Additional notes for several species are presented.

Abbreviations: m. – male exemplar/s; s. – specimen/s; sp./ spp. – species (and subspecies); A.P. – Aleksi Petrov; A.V. – Aleksandar Valkanov; B.G. – Borislav Guéorguiev; B.P. – Bruno Pittioni; B.U. – Blaga Urumova; B.Z. – Boyana Zaharieva; D.I. – Dimitar Ioakimov; G.P. – Georgi Paspaley; I.B. – Ivan Buresch; Il. – Ilchev; J.G. – Julius Ganey; J.M. – Julius Milde; Kr. – Krupka; M.I. – Mihail Iosifov; N.A. – Neno Atanasov; N.K. – Nikolai Karnoschitzky; N.N. – Nikola Nedelkov; N.V. – N. Vihodtzevskij; P.T. – Petar Tschorbadjiev; P.D. – Pencho Drenski; S.L. – Stoyan Lazarov; S.M. – Sofia Kantarjieva-Minkova; T.I. – Teodora Ivanova; T.L. – Toshko Ljubomirov; T.P. – Tsolo Peschev; Ts. – Tsvetkov; V.G. – Vassil Guéorguiev; V.D. – Vanya Dimova; V.Dr. – V. Dramchev; V.K. – Vera Krasteva.

List of species

Ontophylus affinis Redtenbacher, 1849

Bulgaria: Malashevska planina Mtn., E of Igralishte Village, 730 m, 15.03-16.04.2003, 1 s., 16.04-04.05.2003, 1 s., leg. S.L., T.L.; Lake near Varna, 24.11.1951, 1 s. in leaf litter leg. N.K.; **Greece:** Burun-Gyol, 12.11.1942, 2 s., leg. N.V. (KARNOSCHITZKY, 1959).

Note: First record for the Malashevska planina Mtn.

Epiurus comptus (Erichson, 1834)

Bulgaria: Varna, 13.04.1958, 1 s. in a rotten stump, leg. N.K.; **Greece:** Mesta River, 07.11.1942, leg. N.V., 9 s. (KARNOSCHITZKY, 1959, sub *Epiurus* (sic!) *comptus* Er.).

Note: New for the Bulgarian fauna.

Pseudepiurus italicus (Paykull, 1811)

Bulgaria: Varna, 06.04.1958, 4 s. in a rotten stump/ 13.04.1958, 2 s. in a rotten stump/ 20.04.1958, 1 s. in a rotten stump, leg. N.K.

Note: This is the second record for the fauna of Bulgaria.

Tribalus minimus (Rossi, 1790)

Bulgaria: Louda Kamchiya River, 02.05.1958, 1 s., leg. N.K. (GUEORGIEV, 1990); Nessebar, 23.06.1954, 1 s., leg. A.V.; Malashevska planina Mtn., E of Gorna Breznitsa Village, 300-400 m, 03.05.2003, 2 s. in leaf litter of *Platanus orientalis*, leg. B.G.

Note: This is the first record for the Malashevska planina Mtn.

Hololepta plana (Sulzer, 1776)

Bulgaria: Botanical Garden in Sofia, 21.04.1933, 45 s., leg. N.A.; Longosa, 24.09.1949, 1 s., leg. S.M.; Petrich, April 1954, 1 s., leg. T.P.; Rupite, 01.03.1982, 5 s., leg. J.G. (GUÉORGUEV, 1990).

Note: This is the first record for the Sofia region.

***Platysoma compressum* (Herbst, 1783) {= *depressum* Fabricius, 1787}**

Bulgaria: Touria, 07.08.1898, 1 s., leg. D.I. (IOAKIMOV, 1904, sub *Platysoma depressum* F.); Sredna Gora Mtn., 18.08.1905, 7 s.; Tundzha Valley, 08.08.1909, 1 s.; **Slovakia:** N. Baňa, June 1953, 1 s., leg. Kr.

Note: This is the first record for the regions of Sakar and Tundzha valley.

***Eblisia minor* (Rossi, 1792)**

New records: Lakatnik, 11.06.1943, 2 s.; **Slovakia:** Vysok Tatry, July 1954, 1 s., leg. Kr.

***Margarinotus brunneus* (Fabricius, 1775) {= *cadaverinus* (Hoffmann, 1803)}**

Bulgaria: Razgrad, sub *Hister cadaverinus* Hoffm. (MARKOVICH, 1909); Suhodol, 02.04.1901, 1 s., leg. D.I. (IOAKOMOV, 1904); Kuru-Baglar (Sofia), May 1903, 2 s., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909a)/ 10.05.1904, 1 s.; Sofia, 20.03.1905, 1 s., leg. D.I./ October 1905, 6 s., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909a)/ 25.04.1912, 1 s., leg. B.U./ 1925, 1 s., leg. P.T.; Vitosha Mtn., 19.07.1961, 1 s., leg. S.M.; Plovdiv, 4 s., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909a, sub *Hister* (= *Margarinotus*) *terricola* Germ., misidentified)/ 2 s. leg. N.N.; Stara Zagora, 05-06.1906, 3 s., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909a)/ May 1907, 1 s., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909a)/ 1 s. leg. N.N.; Krichim, 07.06.1942, 1 s., leg. I.B.; Malashevka planina Mtn., Gorna Breznitsa Village, 600-1000 m, 09.07.2002, 1 s., leg. B.G.; Varna, 29.03.1947, 3 s./ 30.03.1947, 2 s./ 20.04.1947, 5 s. in dung of *Equus*/ 24.04.1947, 1 s. 30.04.1947, 4 s. on a dead hedgehog (*Erinaceus*)/ 19.05.1947, 2 s. on dead *Talpa*/ 23.04.1949, 1 s./ 03.04.1955, 9 s. on a dead dog, leg. N.K.; Zvezditsa near Varna, 02.05.1949, 16 s. on a carcass, leg. N.K.; Iovkovo near Varna, 20.07.1947, 2 s. on dead *Pica pica*, leg. N.K.; Pomorie, 02.05.1948, 1 s. on the west coast of the salt lake, leg. N.K.

Note: First records for the West Rhodopes (Krichim), Vitosha and Malashevka planina mountains, and the Black Sea Coast.

***Margarinotus bipustulatus* (Schrank, 1781) {= *fimetarius* Herbst, 1792}**

Bulgaria: Svishtov, 04-05.1950, 1 s., leg. N.A.; Varna, 01.04.1943, 8 s./ 07.04.1943, 3 s./ 23.04.1949, 1 s., leg. N.K.; Beloslav near Varna, 03.05.1955, 1 s., leg. N.K.; Zvezditsa near Varna, 02.05.1949, 1 s., leg. N.K.; Vladislavovo near Varna, 28.04.1957, 1 s., leg. N.K.

Note: First records for the Central Danubian Plane and the North Black Sea Coast.

***Margarinotus obscurus* (Kugelann, 1792) {= *stercorarius* (Hoffmann, 1803)}**

Bulgaria: Svishtov, July 1900, 1 s., leg. D.I.; Murgasch, 24.05.1958, 1 s., leg. A.P.; Sofia, 07.04.1913, 1 s./ 3 s. leg. N.N.; Vitosha Mtn., 700 m, 21.05.1939, 1 s., leg. B.P.; Stara Zagora, 05-06.1906, 1 s., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909a)/ 1908, 1 s., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909a)/ 2 s., leg. N.N.; Malashevka planina Mtn., W of Gorna Breznitsa Village, 600-1000 m, 01.05.2003, 1 s., leg. B.G.; Malashevka planina Mtn., W of Gorna Breznitsa Monastery, 600-1000 m, 02.05.2003, 1 s., leg. B.G.; Malashevka planina Mtn., E of Igralishte Village, 730 m, 16.04-04.05.2003, 1 s., leg. S.L., T.L.; Rhodopes Mtn., Belovo, 1 s. leg. J.M.; **Turkey:** Takir-Dagh, near Ganos, 800 m, 06.05.1918, 1 s., leg. I.B.

Note: First records for the Central Danubian Plane, and the West Stara Planina, Vitosha, Malashevka planina and West Rhodopes mountains.

***Margarinotus carbonarius* (Hoffman, 1803)**

Bulgaria: Parschevitsa near Vratsa, 13.07.1966, 1 s., leg. B.Z.

***Margarinotus neglectus* (Germar, 1813)**

Bulgaria: Sofia, 30.09.1903, 1 s., leg. D.I. (IOAKIMOV, 1904); Vitosha, Knyazhevo, 1 s., leg. N.N.

Note: This is the first record for the Vitosha Mtn.

***Margarinotus purpurascens* (Herbst, 1792)**

Bulgaria: Gorni Lozen, May 1958, 1 s.; Stara Zagora, 6 s., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909a); Haskovo, 16.05.1905, 1 s., leg. D.I.; Beloslav, 15.05.1952, 1 s., leg. N.K.; Varna, 01.04.1943, 2 s./ 23.04.1949 2 s./ 02.05.1949, 1 s./ 08.05.1949, 1 s./ 29.03.1953, 1 s., leg. N.K.; Zvezditsa, 02.05.1949, 1 s., leg. N.K.

Note: This is the first record for the Eastern Rhodopes.

***Margarinotus ventralis* (Marseul, 1854)**

Bulgaria: Kom Peak near Berkovitsa, 11.07.1966, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Parschevitsa near Vratsa, 13.07.1966, 3 s., leg. B.Z.; Brestnishka Laka near Teteven, 14.08.1969, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Sofia, 18.05.1902, 1 s., leg. D.I. (IOAKOMOV, 1904); Sliven, 20.05.1969, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Varnicata near Pazardzhik, 26.07.1969, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Yazovir Vasil Kolarov, 26.07.1967, 2 s., leg. B.Z. (GUÉORGUIEV, 1990); Chudnite Mostove near Smolyan, 29.07.1965, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Danoto near Peshtera, 21.07.1967, 4 s., leg. B.Z.; Beglika, 27.07.1969, 2 s., leg. B.Z.

Note: First records for the Central Stara Planina Mtn. and Thracian Lowland.

***Pactolinus major* (Linnaeus, 1767)**

Bulgaria: Sliven, April 1915, 1 s., leg. P.T.; Burgas, 27.09.1909, 1 s., leg. P.T.; **Turkey:** Tekir-Dagh near Sahar Kjol, 05.05.1913, 1 s., leg. I.B.; **Greece:** Korfu (Kerkira) Is., Paleokastritsa, 22.06.1902, 1 s.

Note: First records for the Central Stara Planina Mtn. and the South Black Sea Coast.

***Pachylister inequalis* (Olivier, 1789)**

Bulgaria: Svishtov, July 1899, 1 s., leg. D.I.; Razgrad, 1 s.; Aleksandrovo near Schumen, 13.10.1963, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Granitovo near Belogradchik, 24.05.1966, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Belogradchik, 04.07.1963, 2 s./ 06.07.1963, 5 s./ 22.05.1966, 1 s., leg. B.Z./ 19.09.1964, 1 s., leg. V.K.; Vedrenika near Belogradchik, 17.09.1963, 1 s./ 18.06.1964, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Lom River near Belogradchik, 20.09.1964, 1 s., leg. V.K.; Karmiatitsa near Belogradchik, 18.09.1964, 1 s., leg. V.K.; Vraschka Chuka near Kula, 16.06.1964, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Rakovischki Monastery, near Belogradchik, 17.09.1964, 2 s./ 14.09.1965, 1 s., leg. V.K.; Chuprene Village near Belogradchik, 19.09.1965, 1s./ 22.05.1966, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Berkovitsa, 09.07.1963, 14 s./ 10.07.1963, 5 s./ 12.07.1963, 5 s./ 22.09.1963, 1 s. / 9.09.1965, 1 s., leg. V.K./ 27.06.1965, 1 s., leg. V.Dr.; Klisurski Monastery near Berkovitsa, 10.07.1963, 2 s./ 25.09.1963, 1 s./ 19.06.1964, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Varschets (= Zanozhene) near Berkovitsa, 22.06.1964, 8 s., leg. B.Z.; Begova Livada area near Berkovitsa, 19.09.1965, 1 s., leg. V.K.; Begovitsa area near Berkovitsa, 19.05.1966, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Parschevitsa near Vratsa, 14.09.1964, 1 s., leg. V.K.; Bulchino Prohod near Godech, 29.06.1965, 1 s., leg. V.Dr.; Iskarsko defile, 26.05.1966, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Vitinya,

19.09.1964, 1 s., leg. V.K.; Bresdnischka Laka near Teteven, 14.08.1969, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Gara Anton, 26.07.1972, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Troyan, 15.05.1972, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Panicite near Kalofer, 17.08.1969, 1 s./ 03.09.1970, 1 s./ 09.11.1971, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Karandila near Sliven, 20.05.1964, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Geravna Village near Sliven, 24.08.1969, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Kotel, 22.07.1972, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Bania Village near Burgas, 24.07.1972, 15 s., leg. B.Z.; Sofia, 2 s., leg. N.N./ 07.06.1909, 1 s., leg. Markovich; Vitosha Mtn., 700 m, 21.05.1939, 1 s., leg. B.P.; Karnare, 19.07.1972, 1 s., leg. V.K.; Turia Village near Kazanlak, 1923, 1 s., leg. D.I.; Tsrancha near Pazardzhik, 21.05.1963, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Debrastitsa Village near Pazardzhik, 21.05.1963, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Plovdiv, 1 s., leg. N.N.; Asenovgrad, 16.05.1963, 3 s., leg. B.Z.; Stara Zagora, 05.1907, 1 s., leg. D.I./ 2 s. leg. N.N.; Svilengrad, 19.06.1963, 4 s./ 20.06.1963, 2 s./ 19.06.1963, 4 s./ 20.06.1963, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Belila Village near Grudovo, 22.06.1966, 3 s., leg. B.Z.; Grudovo, 15.08.1967, 4 s./ 12.07.1967, 4 s./ 11.07.1967, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Malashevka planina Mtn., Tsaparevo Village, 480 m, 02-30.07.2002, 1 s., leg. S.L., T.L./ W of Gorna Breznitsa Village, 600-1000 m, 18-20.06.2003, 3 s., leg. B.G.; Petrich, 15.05.1973, 1 s./ 19.05.1973, 1 s./ 21.05.1973, 1 s./ 20.07.1973, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Satovcha near Blagoevgrad, 23.07.1965, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Dospat, 24.07.1965, 3 s./ 26.08.1965, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Trigrad, 29.06.1964, 7 s., leg. B.Z.; Smolyan, 24.07.1964, 1 s./ 26.07.1965, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Kurdzhali, 25.05.1964, 2 s./ 30.05.1965, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Zarevez near Kurdzhali, 23.07.1964, 7 s., leg. B.Z.; Protigerovo near Kurdzhali, 23.07.1964, 3 s., leg. B.Z.; Momchilgrad, 31.05.1965, 4 s., leg. V.K.; Izgrev Village near Momchilgrad, 09.08.1967, 5 s., leg. B.Z.; Meden Buk Village near Krumovgrad, 20.07.1964, 1 s./ 16.07.1967, 6 s., leg. B.Z.; Topolka near Krumovgrad, 01.06.1965, 2 s., leg. V.K.; Snyagodin near Krumovgrad 02.06.1965, 1 s., leg. V.K.; Ivailovgrad, 21.05.1964, 1 s./ 26.07.1964, 4 s./ 18.06.1969, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Mandritza Village near Ivailovgrad, 22.04.1964, 3 s./ 18.07.1964, 2 s./ 19.06.1969, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Varna, 06.06.1954, 2 s. in the dung of *Equus*/ 30.05.1955, 1 s., leg. N.K.; Kaliakra, 05.06.1941, 1 s., leg. P.D.; Karnobat, 01.05.1948, 1 s., leg. N.K.; Arkutino near Burgas, 26.06.1966, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Lesen Village, near Burgas, 13.07.1967, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Primorsko, 13.08.1967, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Primorsko, 17.06.1965, 4 s., leg. B.Z.; Losenets near Burgas, 28.06.1966, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Tsarevo, 11.08.1967, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Sozopol-Ahtopol, 12-15.07.1920, 1 s., leg. Il.; Ahtopol, near Burgas, 16.06.1967, 2 s./ 17.06.1968, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Sinemoretz, near Burgas, 10.08.1967, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Resovo Village, 10.08.1967, 1 s., leg. B.Z.

Note: First records for the Western and Central Danubian Plane, the Central Stara planina Mtn., Vitosha Mtn., Podbalkan, Bakadzhik-Burgas Region and Sandanski-Petrich Valley.

***Hister illigeri* Duftschmid, 1805 {= *sinuatus* Illiger, 1798}**

Bulgaria: Mezdra, 10.06.1906, 1 s., leg. N.N.; Sofia, 3 s., leg. N.N./ 04.04.1909, 1 s./ August 1929, 1 s.; Vitosha, 800 m, 30.05.1939, 1 s., leg. B.P.; Longosa, 22.05.1949, 1 s., leg. N.K.; Pazardzhik, 5 s., leg. N.N.; Malashevka planina Mtn., W of Gorna Breznitsa Village, 600-1000 m, 18-20.06.2003, 2 s., leg. B.G.; Momchilgrad, 04.04.1905, 1 s.; Varna, 02.05.1954, 1 s., leg. N.K./ 09.06.1957, 1 s., leg. N.K.; Vladimirovo near Varna, 28.04.1957, 1 s./ 12.05.1957, 1 s., leg. N.K.

Note: This is the first record for the Sofia region and the Vitosha Mtn.

***Hister quadrimaculatus* Linnaeus, 1758 {= *sinuatus* Herbst, 1792}**

Bulgaria: Razgrad, 1 s., sub *Hister sinuatus* F. (misidentified) = *Margarinotus bipustulatus* (Schränk) (MARKOVICH, 1904; 1909); The collection comprises altogether 115 identified

specimens from the following localities and areas: Razgrad (1 s.), Tervel (2 s.), Shumen (2 s.), Lukovit (2 s.), Sliven (3 s.), Kazanlak (3 s.), Lyulin Mtn. (4 s.), Dragoman (1 s.), Sofia (15 s.), Vitosha Mtn. (8 s.), Thrace (23 s.), West Rhodopes (3 s.), East Rhodopes (5 s.), Malashevka planina Mtn. (1 s.), Slavyanka Mtn. (2 s.), Sakar Mtn. (2 s.), Strandzha Mtn. (9 s.), North Black Sea Coast (11 s.), South Black Sea Coast (20 s.), **Greece:** (Xanthi, 1 s., Saros, 1 s.), **Macedonia:** (Kavadarsko 1 s.), that have been collected between May and September.

Note: First record for the Central Predbalkan, Podbalkan region, Sofia region, Sakar-Tundzha region, Bakadzhishki Heights-Burgas region, Vitosha, Malashevka planina and Slavyanka Mts.

Hister quadrinotatus Scriba, 1790

Bulgaria: Chirpan, 1 s., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909; 1909a sub *Hister quadrimaculatus* Linnaeus misidentified); Varna, 07.04.1943 1 s./ 20.04.1947, 2 s./ 30.04.1950, 1 s./ 02.05.1950, 2 s./ 29.03.1953, 1 s./ 26.04.1953, 1 s./ 17.05.1953, 3 s., leg. N.K.

Note: First record for the North Black Sea Coast.

Hister sepulchralis Erichson, 1854

Bulgaria: Svishtov, July 1900, 1 s., leg. D.I.; Sofia, 1 s., leg. N.N.; Kurilo, 01.04.1900, 1 s.; Gorna Banya, 16.04.1913, 1 s.; Gorno Malovo, 17.04.1951, 2 s., leg. P.D.; Malashevka planina Mtn., W of Gorna Breznitsa Monastery, 600-1000 m, 02.05.2003, 1 s., leg. B.G.; Beloslav, 02.05.1949, 1 s./ 30.05.1955, 2 s., leg. N.K.; Varna, 20.04.1947, 1 s./ 27.04.1947, 2 s./ 23.04.1949, 3 s./ 30.04.1950, 1 s./ 04.05.1952/ 26.04.1953, 3 s., leg. N.K.; Varna, 12.05.1955, 1 s., leg. N.K.; Zvezditsa near Varna, 02.05.1949, 2 s., leg. N.K.

Note: First record for the Central Danubian Plane.

Hister teter Truqui, 1852

Bulgaria: Mandritsa Village near Ivailovgrad, 19.07.1964, 1 s., leg. B.Z.

Note: This is the second record for the fauna of Bulgaria.

Hister unicolor Linnaeus, 1758

Bulgaria: Vraschka Chuka near Kula, 16.05.1964, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Chuprene near Belogradchik, 08.07.1966, 3 s., leg. B.Z.; Kom Peak near Berkovitsa, 11.07.1966, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Klisurski Monastery near Berkovitsa, 10.07.1963, 8 s., leg. B.Z.; Golyama Reka near Berkovitsa, 22.04.1964, 1 s., leg. V.K.; Varschets (= Zanozhene) near Berkovitsa, 22.06.1964, 4 s., leg. B.Z.; Parschevitsa near Vratsa, 13.07.1966, 3 s., leg. B.Z.; Petrevene Village near Lovech, 14.05.1972, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Brestnischka Laka area near Teteven, 14.08.1965, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Kusch-Bunar, near Sliven, 20.05.1969, 3 s., leg. B.Z.; Zelenik area near Kotel, 25.08.1969, 5 s., leg. B.Z.; Kotel, 22.07.1972, 4 s., leg. V.D.; Pobit Kamak area near Pazardzhik, 27.07.1969, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Rhodopes, Yundola, 23.08.1965, 1 s., leg. V.K./ 23.07.1967, 7 s., leg. B.Z.; Beglica area near Velingrad, 27.07.1967, 9 s., leg. B.Z.; Yasovir Vasil Kolarov, 26.07.1967, 5 s., leg. B.Z.; Danoto near Peshtera, 21.07.1967, 4 s., leg. B.Z.; Satovcha near Blagoevgrad, 23.07.1965, 4 s., leg. B.Z.; Trigrad, 29.06.1967, 3 s., leg. B.Z.; Prohled near Smolyan, 27.07.1965, 3 s., leg. B.Z.; Smolyan Lakes, 24.07.1964, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Pelevun near Ivailovgrad, 05.06.1965, 4 s., leg. V.K.; Ivailovgrad, 26.07.1964, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Burschama near Primorsko, 17.06.1965, 1 s., leg. B.Z.

Note: First records for the West Danubian Plane, Thracian Lowland, and the Rhodopes.

***Atholus bimaculatus* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Bulgaria: Lyulin, 800 m, 15.02.1938, 1 s., leg. B.P.; Stara Zagora, 1 s. leg. N.N.; Varna, 3 s., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909b); **Greece:** Kavala, 18.04.1943, 1 s., leg. N.K. (KARNOSCHITZKY, 1959).

***Atholus corvinus* (Germar, 1817)**

Bulgaria: Luda Kamchiya River, 02.05.1958, 1 s., leg. N.K., det. Kryzhanovskij; Dragoman, 02.04.1904, 1 s., leg. D.I.; Sredna Gora Mtn., Panagyuriste, 02.06.1996, 1 s., leg. S.L.; Sofia, April 1906, 5 s., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909a); Stara Zagora, 1 s., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909a); Vinita near Varna, 07.04.1957, 1 s. in dung of *Equus*, leg. N.K.

Note: This is the first record for the Sredna Gora Mtn.

***Atholus duodecimstriatus duodecimstriatus* (Schrank, 1781)**

New records: Bulgaria: Parschevitsa near Vratsa, 13.07.1966, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Panicite near Kalofer, 18.08.1969, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Banya Village near Burgas, 24.07.1972, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Isgrev Village near Momchilgrad, 09.08.1967, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Meden Buk Village near Krumovgrad, 16.07.1967, 2 s., leg. B.Z.; Resovo Village near Burgas, 10.08.1967, 1 s., leg. B.Z.

Note: This is the first record for the South Black Sea Coast.

***Atholus duodecistriatus quatuordecimstriatus* Kryzhanovskij, 1976**

New records: Bulgaria: Panicite near Kalofer, 18.08.1969, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Sofia, 15.05.1912, 1 s.; Gorni Lozen, May 1958, 1 s.; Sinemorets Village near Burgas, 10.08.1967, 1 s., leg. B.Z.; Resovo Village near Burgas, 10.08.1967, 2 s., leg. B.Z.

Note: This is the first record for the South Black Sea Coast.

***Dendrophilus punctatus championi* Lewis, 1886**

New records: Bulgaria: Malashevska Planina Mtn., W of Gorna Breznitsa Village, 600-1000 m, 01.05.2003, 1 s., leg. B.G.

Note: This is the first record for the Malashevska Planina Mtn.

***Platylomalus complanatus* (Panzer, 1792)**

Bulgaria: Dalgopol, 24.11.1947, 6 s., leg. N.K.; Longoza, 23.09.1949, 1 s., leg. N.K.; **Greece:** Mesta River, 07.11.1942, 1 s., leg. N.V.

Note: This is the second record for the fauna of Bulgaria.

***Paromalus flavicornis* (Herbst, 1792)**

Bulgaria: Kocherinovo, 30.06.1943, 1 s.

Note: This is the first record for the region of Boboschevo-Simitli.

***Chaetabraeus convexus* (Reitter, 1884)**

Bulgaria: Varna, 22.10.1944, 2 s. under a stone/ 25.02.1950, 17 s. under a stone/ 13.02.1951, 1 s./ 14.02.1951, 2 s. in leaf litter/ 17.10.1954, 1 s., leg. N.K.

Note: This is the second record for the fauna of Bulgaria.

***Abraeus perpusillus* (Marsham, 1802)**

New records: Varna, 20.04.1958, 1 s. in a rotten stump, leg. N.K.

Note: This is the second record for the fauna of Bulgaria.

***Acritus minutus* (Herbst, 1792)**

Bulgaria: Bilka Village (= Chiflik), 22.11.1953, 1 s. under the bark of an old oak stump, leg. N.K.; **Greece:** Mesta River, 07.11.1942, 2 s. leg. N.V. (KARNOSCHITZKY, 1959, sub *Acritus punctum* Aubé, misidentified).

Note: This is the first record for the East Stara Planina Mtn.

***Acritus nigricornis* (Hoffmann, 1803)**

Bulgaria: Varna, 27.02.1949, 3 s./ 02.09.1950, 3 s./ 10.09.1950, 1 s./ 17.10.1954, 2 s. in leaf litter, leg. N.K./ 28.05.1954, 1 s./ 30.03.1958, 1 s. in the dry dung of *Bos*, leg. N.K.

Note: This is the second record for the fauna of Bulgaria.

***Teretrius fabricii* Mazur, 1972**

Bulgaria: Eastern Danubian plane, Harsovo Village near Ispereh (= Kemanlar), 28.08.1934, 3 s. in the beams of the houses/ 12.01.1935, 1 s. in "woods of oak"/ 02.10.1936, 4 s. in an oak beam/ 08.1936, 1 s. in an oak beam, leg. P.T., det. Bryant.

Note: This species is new to the Bulgarian fauna.

***Gnathoncus nannetensis* (Marseul, 1862)**

Bulgaria: Yantra Valley, near Tarnovo, cave Prilepnata, 24.04.1995, 1 s., leg. T. I.; Varna, 24.04.1947, 1 s., leg. N.K.

Note: Second record from Bulgaria.

***Gnathoncus rotundatus* (Kugelann, 1792) {= *nannus* (Scriba, 1790)}**

Bulgaria: Knyazhevo, 23.07.1902, 1 s., leg. D.I. (IOAKIMOV, 1904); Sofia, 01.05.1902, 1 s. leg. D.I. (IOAKIMOV, 1904); Varna, 14.06.1953, 1 s., leg. N.K.

Note: First record for the North Black Sea Coast.

***Saprinus aegialius* Reitter, 1884**

Bulgaria: Varna, 23.09.1950, 2 m., leg. Ts.

***Saprinus aeneus* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Bulgaria: Sofia, 02.05.1901, 1 m., leg. D.I. (IOAKIMOV, 1904); Varna, 18.08.1944, 1 m., leg. N.K.; Iovkovo near Varna, 20.07.1947, 1 m., leg. N.K.

Note: First record for the North Black Sea Coast.

***Saprinus furvus* Erichson, 1834**

Bulgaria: Svishtov, July 1900, 2 s., leg. D.I.; Varna, 18.08.1944, 12 s./ 18.08.1944, 1 s., leg. N.K./ 30.04.1950, 1 s., leg. Ts./ 23.09.1950, 1 s., leg. Ts./ 30.05.1955, 1 s., leg. N.K.

Note: First record for the Central Danube Plane.

***Saprinus georgicus* Marseul, 1862**

Bulgaria: Varna, 18.08.1944, 1 m., leg. N.K.

***Saprinus maculatus* (Rossi, 1790)**

Bulgaria: Svishtov, July 1900, 1 s., leg. D.I.; Stara Zagora, 1 s., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909); Burgas, 06.06.1910, 1 s.

Note: First record for the South Black Sea Coast.

***Saprinus planiusculus* Motschulsky, 1849**

Bulgaria: Varna, 18.08.1944, 1 m. on dead *Testudo*, leg. N.K.; Zvezditsa, 02.05.1949, 1 m., leg. N.K.; Varna, 02.05.1950, 1 m., leg. N.K.

Note: First record for the North Black Sea Coast.

***Saprinus politus* (Brahm, 1790)**

Bulgaria: Varna, 23.09.1950, 1 m. leg. Ts. / 09.08.1953, 1 m., leg. N.K.

Note: This species is new to the Bulgarian fauna.

***Saprinus semipunctatus* (Fabricius, 1792)**

Bulgaria: Svishtov, July 1900, leg. D.I.; Sofia, 09.07.1927, 1 m., leg. D.I.; Varna, 26.06.1946, 1 m., leg. N.K./ 23.09.1950, 4 m. on dead crayfishes, leg. Ts./ 09.08.1953, 10 m. on dead *Sus*, leg. N.K.; Nessebar, 23.06.1954, 2 m., leg. A.V.; Sozopol, on the seacoast, 02.07.1958, 1 m. on a carcass, leg. N.K.

***Saprinus semistratus* (Scriba, 1790)**

Bulgaria: Sofia, 1 m., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909a, sub *Saprinus subnitidus* Marseul, misidentified); Plovdiv, 1 m., leg. N.N. (NEDELKOV, 1909a); Varna, 08.1941, 1 m., leg. A.V./ 19.08.1946, 1 m. on a dead shrew, / 19.05.1947 1 m. on dead *Talpa*/ 02.05.1950, 1 m./ 02.05.1950, 1 m./ 09.08.1953, 2 m. on dead *Sus*, leg. N.K.; Iovkovo near Varna, 20.07.1947, 1 m. on dead *Pica pica*/ 20.07.1947, 1 m. on dead *Pica pica*, leg. N.K.

Note: First record for the North Black Sea Coast.

***Saprinus subnitescens* Bickhardt, 1909**

Bulgaria: Sofia, 1 m., leg. N.N.; Plovdiv, 2 m., leg. N.N.; Varna, 15.07.1939, Sv. Konstantin, 7 m., leg. P.D.; Varna, 12.08.1941, 2 m. leg. A.V./ 13.08.1944, 1 m. on dead *Felis*, leg. N.V. / 18.08.1944, 1 m. on dead *Testudo*/ 18.08.1944, 5 m. on dead *Testudo*, leg. N.K./ 19.08.1946, 2 m. on dead shrew, leg. N.K./ 24.04.1947, 1 m., leg. N.K./ 30.04.1947, 1 m. on dead *Talpa*, leg. N.K./ 19.05.1947, 5 m. on dead *Talpa*, leg. N.K./ 19.05.1947, 2 m. on dead *Talpa*, leg. N.K./ 03.04.1950, 1 m. on dead *Anser*, leg. N.K./ 02.05.1950, 1 m., leg. N.K./ 02.05.1950, 1 m., leg. N.K./ 23.09.1950, 2 m. on dead crayfishes, leg. Ts./ 23.09.1950, 2 m. on dead crayfishes, leg. Ts.; 09.08.1953, 12 m. on dead *Sus*, leg. N.K.; Beloslav (= Gebedzhe), 20.07.1947, 1 m. on the coast of the lake, leg. N.K.; Iovkovo near Varna, 20.07.1947, 3 m. on dead *Pica pica*, leg. N.K.; Zvezditsa near Varna, 02.05.1949, 1 m., leg. N.K.

***Saprinus tenuistrius sparsutus* Solsky, 1876**

Bulgaria: Stara Zagora, 1 m., leg. N.N.

Note: Second record for Bulgaria.

***Saprinus vermiculatus* Reichardt, 1923**

Bulgaria: Varna, 29.03.1947, 1 m., leg. N.K.

Note: This species is new to the Bulgarian fauna.

***Saprinus virescens* (Paykull, 1798)**

Bulgaria: Sofia, 2 s., leg. N.N.; Varna, 24.09.1947, 1 s., leg. N.K.; Beloslav near Varna, 15.05.1952, 1 s., leg. Ts.

***Euspilotus perrisi* (Marseul, 1872)**

Bulgaria: Marten Village near Rouse, 28.07.1958, 2 s. in the nest of *Merops apiaster*, leg. V.G, det. Krizhanovskij (GUEORGIEV, 1990); Sofia, 03.07.1934, 2 s., leg. P.D.

Note: First record for the Sofia region.

***Chalcionellus amoenus* (Erichson, 1834)**

Bulgaria: Pobiti Kamani near Varna, 13.08.1950, 2 s. in the dung of *Bos*, leg. N.K. (MAZUR, 1970).

***Chalcionellus decemstriatus* (Rossi, 1792)**

Bulgaria: Louda Kamchiya River, 02.05.1958, 1 s., leg. & det. N.K.; Vitosha Mt., 800 m, 30.06.1939, 1 s., leg. B.P.; Malashevskia planina Mtn., W of Gorna Breznitsa Village, 600-1000 m, 18-20.06.2003, 1 s., leg. B.G.; Varna, 24.04.1947, 1 s. in the dung of *Equus*/ 17.05.1953, 9 s. in the dung of *Equus*, leg. N.K.;

Note: First record for the Vitosha Mtn.

***Pholioxenus schatzmayri* (J. Müller, 1910)**

Bulgaria: Beloslav-Esero, 01.08.1951, 2 s. in the nest of *Glis*, leg. N.K.

Note: This species is new to the Bulgarian fauna.

***Hypocacculus rubripes* (Erichson, 1834)**

Bulgaria: Louda Kamchiya River, 02.05.1958, 1 s., leg. N.K., det. Krizhanovskij; Shabla, 08.05.1949, 7 s., leg. N.K.; Karaman, 09.05.1943, 1 s., leg. Karnoschitsky; Varna, Sv. Konstantin, 15.07.1939, 1 s., leg. P.D.; Varna, 18.07. 1944, 1 s. on dead dolphin/ 18.08.1944, 3 s. on dead *Testudo*/ 31.05.1947, 1 s., leg. N.K./ 19.09.1945, 1 s., leg. M.I.; Zvezditsa, 02.05.1949, 1 s., leg. N.K.; Nessebar, 15.08.1948, 1 s., leg. M.I./ 23.06.1953, 11 s., leg. N.K./ 23.06.1954, 4 s., leg. A.V; Sozopol, 11.10.1948, 2 s., leg. M.I.; **Greece:** Kum-Burun, 10.05.1943, 2 s. leg. A.V. (KARNOSCHITZKY, 1959, sub *Saprinus* (*Hypocaccus*) *rubripes* Er.)/ 10.05.1943, 1 s. leg. A.V. (KARNOSCHITZKY, 1959, sub *Hypocacculus metallicus* (Hbst.), misidentified)/ 10-11.05.1953, leg. A.V.; Keramoti, May 1943, leg. A.V. (KARNOSCHITZKY, 1959).

Note: First record for the East Stara Planina Mtn.

***Hypocacculus rufipes* (Kugelann, 1792)**

Bulgaria: Shabla, 25.05.1958, 1 s., leg. N.K. Varna, 13.03.1944, 1 s. in leaf litter, leg. N.K.

Note: Second record for Bulgaria.

***Hypocaccus crassipes* (Erichson, 1834)**

Bulgaria: Nessebar, 23.06.1953, 1 s., leg. N.K.

Note: Second record for Bulgaria.

***Hypocaccus rugifrons subtilis* (Schmidt, 1884)**

Bulgaria: Kamchiya River, 30.07.1945, 5 s./ 30.07.1947, 6 s. leg. M.I.; Shabla, 23.05.1948, 1 s., leg. A.V.; Beloslav, 02.05.194?, 1 s. on carcass, leg. N.K.; Pobiti kamani, 08.09.1945, 1 s., leg. M.I.; Varna, 15.07.1939, Sv. Konstantin, 5 s., leg. P.D. (DRENSKI, 1942, sub *Saprinus virescens* Paykull, misidentified)/ 01.06.1944, 5 s. on a dead gull/ 18.07.1944, 52 s. on a dead dolphin (KARNOSCHITZKY, 1949)/ 18.08.1944, 60 s. on dead *Testudo*, leg. N.K./ 26.07.1948, 14 s., leg. G.P./ 06.09.1948, 2 s., leg. M.I.; Byala, 05.05.1957, 8 s. on the seacoast, leg. A.V.; Nessebar, 01.06.1920, 1 s., leg. D.I./ 23.06.1954, 11 s., leg. A.V.; Pomorie, 02.05.1948, 3 s., leg. N.K.; Sozopol, 02.07.1958, 29 s. seacoast, on carcass, leg. N.K.

***Hypocaccus dimidiatus* (Illiger, 1807)**

Bulgaria: Aladzha Monastery near Varna, 13.09.1942, 6 s., leg. N.V.; Varna, Sv. Konstantin, July 1939, 1 s., leg. P.D.; Varna, 15.07.1939, 16 s., leg. P.D. (DRENSKI, 1942, sub *Saprinus virescens* Paykull, misidentified); Varna, 15.07.1939, 1 s., leg. P.D. (DRENSKI, 1942, sub *Saprinus semipunctatus* Fabricius, misidentified); Varna, 01.06.1944, 1 s. on dead gull, leg. N.K. (KARNOSCHITZKY, 1949); Varna, 18.08.1944, 1 s. on dead *Testudo*, leg. N.K./ 26.07.1948, 9 s. on the seacoast leg. G.P. (KARNOSCHITZKY, 1949)/ 06.09.1945, 11 s. (KARNOSCHITZKY, 1949)/ 09.09.1945, 10 s., leg. M.I.; **Greece:** Kum-Burun, 10.05.1943, 1 s. leg. A.V. (KARNOSCHITZKY, 1959).

***Exaesiopus grossipes* (Marseul, 1855)**

Bulgaria: Luda Kamchiya River, 02.05.1958, 1 s., leg. N.K., det. Kryzhanovskij (GUEORGUIEV, 1990).

Results

A total of 1266 specimens found in the collection of the NMNHS were examined and identified. Out of this number, another 41 females of the genus *Saprinus* Erichson, which cannot be reliably determined, were reviewed but were not included in the list below. Altogether, 59 species and subspecies from 26 genera were identified, as 5 species were new to the Bulgarian fauna. Two of the genera (*Tereetrius* Erichson and *Pbolioxenus* Reichardt) are also new entries to the country's list. Another 10 species were recorded for the second time from Bulgaria. For another 32 species new data for their regional distribution were added.

It has been found out that some already published specimens of *Margarinotus terricola* Germ. (sub *Hister*) in the regions of Sofia and the Thracian Lowland (NEDELKOV, 1909a) are actually *Margarinotus brunneus*. DRENSKY (1942) recorded *Saprinus semistriatus* and *Saprinus*

virescens from the North Black Sea Coast. After a re-examination of that material the author established that it had been wrongly identified and that it actually refers to *Hypocaccus rugifrons subtilis* (Schmidt) and *Hypocaccus dimidiatus* (Illiger). The study of the material of KARNOSCHITZKY (1959) led to the inference that part of it was incorrectly determined also. As a result of this the following corrections have been done: 1/ the halophilous *Halacritus punctum* Aubé (sub *Acritus*) is in fact the dendrophilous *Acritus minutus* (Hbst.); 2/ *Hypocacculus* (= *Hypocaccus*) *metallicus* (Hbst.) has to be referred as to *Hypocacculus rubripes* (Er.). One of the specimens from Razgrad (MARKOVICH, 1904), identified as *Hister sinuatus* Fabricius (= *Margarinotus bipustulatus* (Schrank)), is in fact *Hister quadrimaculatus* Linnaeus (= *Hister sinuatus* Herbst).

Except from Bulgaria (59 spp.), material from the following countries: Greece – 9 species; Turkey – 2 species; Slovakia – 2 species and Macedonia – 1 species, is recorded.

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**Ревизиран списък на бръмбарите от семейство Histeridae (Coleoptera) в
колекцията на Националния природонаучен музей, София**

Евгени ЧЕХЛАРОВ

(Р е з ю м е)

Настоящото изследване се основава изцяло на материал от колекциите на Националния природонаучен музей в София. Бяха открити и определени общо 1266 екземпляра от 59 вида и 26 рода. Нови за България са 5 вида и 2 рода. Други 10 вида се съобщават за втори път за страната. За 32 от видовете се дават нови данни за тяхното разпространение. При ревизирането на колекцията беше открит погрешно определен материал, на базата на който са съставени научни публикации. Във връзка с това са направени съответните корекции. Установените видове са от следните държави: България - 59 вида, Гърция - 9 вида, Турция - 2 вида, Словакия - 2 вида и Македония - 1 вид.